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The importance of digital transformation in the development of corporate communications

KEYWORDS

digital transformation,
innovation activity,
communication structure,
collective intelligence,
strategic management

ABSTRACT

Introduction. Thus, the era of a fluid society, an elusive world, transitory modernity, online communities, and methodological turns necessitates the need to find new paradigms for company transformation that account for technical, social, structural, value, cognitive, cultural, and psychological aspects to expand the space of opportunities.

The subject of this article is the role of effective communication and the mechanism by which meanings emerge in the collective mind of a complex commercial sociotechnical system.

Materials and methods. The research methodology involves theoretical analysis, synthesis, and combination of scientific concepts to address research issues. The research materials consisted of scientific articles from peer-reviewed periodical publications, including the Journal of the Knowledge Economy, Economics, Entrepreneurship, and Law, as well as The Annals of Regional Science.

Results. The author synthesizes the provisions of traditionally studied fields of knowledge in isolation, including the theory of communication, collective intelligence, corporate culture management, and the theory of motivation in the context of the digital transformation of companies. Analysis of these concepts together provides a deeper understanding of the knowledge acquisition processes necessary to increase the effectiveness of digital transformation. The principles of effective communication management are formulated, contributing to the identification and successful formalization of implicit knowledge. The applied nature of the research is to deepen the understanding of the mechanism behind the emergence of innovative ideas and propose measures to minimize the risks associated with managing the communication system within the organization.

Conclusion. The article may be helpful for researchers whose research interests include innovative trends in management, the development of entrepreneurial activity, and the effectiveness of digitalization in enterprises. The results of the work can also be helpful for practical managers who develop and implement strategies for the innovative development of enterprises.

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INTRODUCTION

In the context of the transition to the sixth technological order, the rate of change is increasing, and the modern economic environment is characterized as a BANI-world (an acronym for English words: brittle, anxious, nonlinear, and incomprehensible). The rapid nature of change necessitates new management approaches that leverage innovative digital technologies, providing new avenues to enhance efficiency. In most markets, the rate of change is growing constantly under the influence of several factors. In such a dynamic environment, it is becoming increasingly important for companies to adapt and utilize changes as opportunities for growth and development.

Digital transformation has evolved from a technological opportunity to a direct necessity due to the rapid development of digital technologies and the global competition for consumers, allowing manufacturers to significantly strengthen and expand their market positions through the development of entrepreneurial approaches and innovations. Successful digitalization offers long-term, positive, and tangible benefits for organizations, making it essential to learn from the experiences of their employees and customers, thereby increasing their engagement through new digital channels [2]. In the field of public administration in the regions of the Russian Federation, improving the digital maturity of public and municipal administration contributes to a multiple improvement in the social and economic security of citizens while maintaining or even reducing budget expenditures, allowing them to move from the logic of catching up to the logic of advancing development [3].

The logic of reality-based business is changing:

- Adaptive models are giving way to more evolutionary preadaptive ones. Anticipating changes and scanning horizons are becoming mandatory in conditions of growing uncertainty.
- Instrumental modernization can no longer provide the required level of efficiency in most cases, giving way to a comprehensive reformation that involves working with social mechanisms of interaction and value orientations.

In personnel management, the emphasis is shifting from the study of employees' human capital to the study of potential, that is, both active and latent opportunities.

In business relations and intra-organizational communication, the logic of "you-to-me, I-to-you" is shifting to the logic of dignity, which means that moral and symbolic capital become more important for the participants in the process.

These trends have varying degrees of relevance and vary across markets, regions, industries, and cultures. Their influence is most substantial in advanced knowledge-intensive industries, which are at the “forefront” of change. Thus, the era of a fluid society, an elusive world, transitory modernity, online communities, and methodological turns dictates the need to find new paradigms for company transformation that take into account technical, social, structural, value, cognitive, cultural, and psychological aspects to expand the space of opportunities.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The paper examines the challenges of communication management in terms of its impact on a company’s adaptive potential and innovative activity during digital transformation. The main research questions were as follows:

How can you foster effective communication within the company?

- How can a designed system of formal and informal communications affect innovation and digital transformation?
- What are the risks involved in developing communication routes within an organization?
- What strategies allow you to minimize risks when managing communications?

The research methodology involves the theoretical analysis, synthesis, and combination of scientific concepts to address research issues. As part of revising the concepts related to the article’s topic, practical recommendations for risk management in communication management within the digital transformation framework were developed.

The research materials consisted of scientific articles from peer-reviewed periodical publications, including the Journal of the Knowledge Economy, Economics, Entrepreneurship and Law, The Annals of Regional Science, Strategic Management Journal, Economic Sciences, Leadership and Management, Sustainability, and the Russian Journal of Industrial Economics, among others.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Digital transformation is a set of actions taken by organizations or countries to introduce new digital technologies, aiming to enhance productivity and focus on disruptive technologies. Organizations need a clear strategy, the proper

organizational structure, digital capabilities, a supportive organizational culture, and a balanced management system to implement digital change [4; 5].

J. Zhang et al. suggest that five factors – internal digital customer needs, industry-specific digital innovations, competitor challenges, digital innovation management, and the needs of the digital age – are driving the digital transformation of human resource management. The authors suggest that digital human resource management processes are closely tied to the implementation of functions such as selection, training, development, and evaluation, utilizing modern digital technologies [6].

J. Erjavec et al. define the primary organizational forms for successful digital transformation. The authors provide a comprehensive understanding of how companies can develop their digital capabilities by combining the various actions of participants, their roles and responsibilities, and their interactions [7].

V. Velyako and S. Musa believe that the biggest obstacle to digital transformation is cultural problems in the organization. The authors demonstrate how digital opportunities, digital innovations, and organizational sustainability serve as an intermediary role between digital organizational culture and competitive advantage [8].

Q. Yao et al. demonstrate that digital transformation has a positive impact on the sustainable growth of firms. Additionally, cross-border search opportunities mitigate the adverse effects of digital transformation on the sustainable growth of firms. At the same time, managerial digital problems also reduce the impact of digital transformation on the sustainable growth of firms [9]. Cross-border search refers to the process of gaining access to information located outside of organizations.

Digitalization removes geographical barriers between consumers and suppliers of goods and services. Technological developments have led to the emergence of international electronic platforms, also known as ecosystems. The ecosystem offers goods and services to customers through electronic distribution channels. B2B ecosystems provide their services to corporate clients [10].

J. Rehman et al. write that professional service firms (PSFs), being knowledge-intensive organizations, often face the challenge of continually improving the competence of their staff, which forms the basis of organizational intellectual capital and provides them with a competitive advantage. The authors offer practical recommendations to knowledge and human resources managers in service companies to achieve high-quality customer service and satisfaction through

the effective use of a competent workforce, as well as to maintain a sustainable competitive advantage [11].

T. Zhang et al. focus on how age and the level of digitalization influence individuals' decisions to become employees or entrepreneurs. The authors found that workers with low and high levels of digitalization are more likely to become entrepreneurs than their colleagues with an average level [12].

Thus, studying the main trends and patterns in the development of corporate communications under the influence of digital technologies will help to understand better how the ways of interaction within organizations and with external partners are changing. Digital tools such as email, instant messengers, and video conferencing speed up the decision-making process and increase work efficiency. Collaboration platforms, such as cloud storage and collaborative document development tools, enable teams to work together on projects regardless of their location. Social media and internal communication platforms help to create a more open and friendly atmosphere within the organization.

THE RESULTS OF THE STUDY

1 Innovation as an adaptation tool

Today, to increase resilience and develop in markets with increasing competition and shorter product life cycles, it is undoubtedly becoming fundamental for enterprises to understand the importance of knowledge management and innovation. Research results indicate that an effective innovation strategy can lead to higher productivity in unstable environments [13]. Thanks to innovations, the changes that are taking place are not threats, but growth opportunities [14]. The modern socio-economic reality encourages commercial structures to explore methods for increasing the productivity of knowledge [15]. The number of areas in which intelligence, creativity, and innovation factors are becoming crucial to a company's survival and success is growing. The need to pay attention to mechanisms that encourage the generation of ideas is driven by two key trends: a decline in the durability of business models and an increase in the frequency of risks. In addition to the mechanisms of knowledge generation, it is essential to consider their transfer and assimilation, namely, the development of relevant competencies [16]. When reforming a specific area of a company's activity – turning accumulated knowledge and experience into capital – it is necessary to take into account the behavior of the learning curve, characterized by growth with saturation (fading exponent).

When analyzing knowledge, for unity of understanding, it is necessary to distinguish the components of the management chain: data, information, knowledge, experience, wisdom, and vision. Data is a representation of information in a formalized form suitable for communication and processing.

Information is knowledge about objects or phenomena in the surrounding world, encompassing uncertainty in the description of their state. Information is data that is placed in context, making it more meaningful and comprehensible.

Knowledge provides a context for perceiving information, enabling you to make informed decisions and take effective action.

Understanding is achieved when one recognizes the boundaries of a specific knowledge application and its semantic integrity.

Wisdom is associated with a wealth of learned contexts. Wisdom enables you to integrate new knowledge into your existing experience.

Vision is the ability to create meaningful imaginary worlds for the implementation of creative strategic analysis and forecasting.

The typology of knowledge implies a division into explicit (formalized) and implicit (non-formalized). Explicit knowledge is transferable and replicable in theories, concepts, practices, and models. Implicit learning is integrated into the inner world of employees. Informal knowledge is transmitted only in the process of communication and joint activities. Externalization is the process of transferring knowledge from an implicit to an explicit form. Internalization is a process that progresses from explicit to implicit, which is known as assimilation.

Thus, in the context of a dynamic transformation of the business environment, knowledge and the ability to manage its flow become the primary value, as it is essential to change quickly and in the right direction.

2 Communication management and collective intelligence

Innovations are born in communication, the form of which is primarily determined by the formal and informal structures of interactions within the organization. The communications carried out inside and around the company can be analyzed at different levels:

- interpersonal, as the interaction of specific personalities;
- intergroup, when each participant in the interaction is considered as a representative of a particular social group.

According to the theory of social identity, the process of realizing group membership involves the following steps:

- social categorization – identification and characterization of groups that make up the social environment;
- social identification – deepening cooperation with several groups, deciding to identify oneself with some of them;
- social identity – functioning as a representative of a group.

Excessive force of unity within social communities can lead to destructive consequences, including reduced mobility, the emergence of favoritism and collective narcissism, increased social competition among groups, and a decrease in the diversity of opinions expressed. Excessive isolation of an employee can lead to a divergence of interests between the team and the individual, resulting in a lack of synergy and a limited vision. The creation of an effective communication system, along with open communication and the exchange of opinions, increases confidence in the solutions developed by the management system. Trust, in turn, is the key to effective implementation of solutions. Interactions generate meanings; the cooperative system enables increased consistency, resulting in greater orderliness and adaptability. An employee, like a Brownian particle, is constantly involved in the processes of collision and exchange of semantic energy, coordinating the trajectory of their further actions.

The paper [17] presents the interpretation of the collective mind as the collective mind of people. Figure 1 schematically shows the areas of distribution of abilities and skills of the two partners. The solid line illustrates the joint ability of the group, the scope of which is much broader than that of the partners in the case of independent activity. Complete overlap makes potential communication meaningless, while the absence of common ground virtually eliminates the possibility of fruitful contact. A person who always agrees does not receive a significant portion of the multidimensional feedback, which limits the information considered when making decisions. Social cognitive convergence and divergence are ongoing processes that occur within an organization, varying in intensity. Divergence in this context refers to an increase in individual diversity and isolation, while convergence refers to symbiosis and cohesion. As a result of the collective pooling of efforts and competencies of the management team, adaptability and strategic flexibility are developed.

Figure 1 The scheme of combining abilities in the co-creation of a group

Thus, a necessary condition for effective social contacts is the uniqueness of the interacting subjects and the difference in their semantic spaces. The mental diversity of community members accumulates quantitatively and evolves into a qualitative one, providing greater adaptability. The disjunction of opinions, meanings, value matrices, and points of view offers an expansion of the multitude of solutions and alternatives visible by the organization. Variability of views can be promoted both extensively and intensively through the development of the psyche and skills that foster productive interaction, pluralism, and meritocracy. A holistic understanding of the current business environment and its development trends is possible with the most multidimensional view and analysis, when correlating the information received with different value perspectives of the world and a diverse system of priorities. The collective mind also allows us to notice a greater number of risks and opportunities.

Intra-organizational, intergroup, and interpersonal differences and similarities are essentially opposite concepts that complement rather than exclude each other. The holistic appearance of an organization is determined by the communicative processes within which individual similarities and differences are combined and transformed. A certain correspondence is necessary for primary understanding; however, not only understanding but also misunderstanding is a prerequisite for helpful communication. The benefit of a communication partner is that they are

different from you; the uniqueness of each participant in the communication process is valuable because it is at the “junctions” that new meanings are generated. A prerequisite for the functioning of a thinking mind, that is, creating ideas and meanings, is the heterogeneity of participants in the organizational structure.

According to the first law of cybernetics, a management system must have a sufficient variety of management methods commensurate with the entropy of the management object. The application of various methods requires people with specific special properties; therefore, the increase in the power of many potential fluctuations and attractors, which invariably occurs in a dynamic modern socio-economic environment, increases the requirements for the degree of cognitive diversity of company employees. Cognitive diversity is defined as the variability of ideas, values, skills, approaches, and experiences among members of an organization.

The cognitive diversity of team members largely determines the team's innovation potential, increasing the degree of emergence of the ergatic system and the limit of possible growth in its goodwill [15]. Diversity is about differences, differences are the ground for conflict, and conflicts [19] are, in many ways, a trigger for development, as they are in confrontation that different positions are considered and the overall corporate strategy is enriched with new meanings. It is essential in this context to reduce the apparent harmful effects of conflicts.

When developing principles for building a communication system that enhances innovation activity, a clause should be introduced about the potential danger of intentions. The side effects of certain actions sometimes turn out to be more important and more useful than the original goal. Creative thinking does not always arise from forcing the brain to work hard and persistently; it also arises as a result of a feeling of relaxation and openness. It is not a fact that by purposefully creating innovation, we will necessarily create innovation. Often, a practical innovation is the result of mistakes and inappropriate activities. Discovery can be the subject of both purposeful searches and genuine interest in a field, or vice versa, or simply indolence – laziness. If employees change the way they do things, he evaluates how the bosses will evaluate this deviation. It is necessary to strike a balance between spontaneity and control, allowing employees to adjust the order of actions and make mistakes, but without incurring critical consequences. As part of a person's life, most learning takes place in a playful manner, driven by motives such as curiosity, fun, interest, pleasure, style, and competition. Thus, strictly directive management models cut off part of the innovation potential.

3 Minimizing the risks of communication management

The first way to minimize risks is through value management. Corporate culture is created through communication. Communication is a means of human interaction, resulting in the creation, transmission, and internalization of customs, roles, rules, rituals, laws, and other patterns of behavior. In a sense, culture is a "remnant" of social communication. To implement an effective system of interaction, it is necessary to introduce values into the company's corporate culture that contribute to breaking the "us-them" dichotomy in intergroup relations, namely, treating the implementation of ideas put forward by different groups as a collaborative effort rather than a zero-sum game. An organizational culture with high synergy encourages actions that strengthen the community of its members. An axiological shift [20] of this kind is tough to implement due to the fundamental characteristics of the phenomenon of corporate culture. Culture needs to be instilled, not preached – it is born in the process of interactions. Corporate culture is the core value of an organization, which largely determines the behavior of employees and, in some cases, motivates them to take specific actions through moral guidelines and the creation of meaning. Crystallization of a stable system of explicitly stated and informally shared guidelines allows an employee to experience fewer internal contradictions, less doubt, and therefore act more willingly, faster, more confidently, and more effectively.

The following method ensures the resilience of the management system in the context of conflict-prone diversity by increasing the level of emotional intelligence among its participants. Emotional intelligence (EQ) [21] is a set of skills and abilities that enable recognizing specific emotionally charged reactions and stimuli, both one's own and those of others. Developed emotional intelligence allows the avoidance of a cumulative effect or the action of a negative feedback loop, thereby mitigating the initially small impact of an adverse event. A cumulative effect in the context of emotional intelligence may arise from the frequent occurrence of work situations with negative emotional connotations.

In this case, the employee accumulates dissatisfaction with even minor events and can form a stable associative link "work = negative". An example is stress from overwork, which, for a specific period, may be perceived as acceptable or even motivating, but not in a sustainable long-term perspective. It should be noted that certain types of risks accumulate. In such a situation, a large number of low-risk events form a significant tail risk. A positive feedback loop is a situation where part of the output signal is fed back to the input and affects the operation. That is, with each cycle, the deviation increases. Regarding emotional intelligence, this mechanism

can destructively manifest itself, for example, in a gradual increase in the degree of mutual intolerance among various groups with conflicting professional interests or in the logic of reciprocity applied not only in positive moments of interaction.

It is advisable to develop the emotional intelligence of employees on a top-down basis, with employees involved in management, including administrative, methodological, operational, and project roles.

Systematic work on developing employees' emotional intelligence not only enhances the intensity of innovation in communications but also yields several other positive consequences: improving the company's business processes, enhancing employee motivation, and increasing productivity.

The main risks associated with the strategy of increasing employees' emotional intelligence are: a lack of systematic efforts, inconsistency between what is declared and what is implemented (the theatricality of the process), conflict with the company's corporate culture, and significant investments in unattractive employees.

To implement a strategy that increases employees' emotional intelligence, regular reassessment and analysis of dynamics are necessary.

Developed emotional intelligence enables an employee to identify internal changes, understand the reasons behind the intentions that lead to specific actions, and determine the true meaning behind these actions, whether it is their own or that of their colleagues. The development of emotional intelligence is not a universal means of preventing conflicts in working relationships. However, it makes conflicts less prolonged and more constructive, thereby improving the communication system among employees. Awareness, in terms of identifying the true factors and cause-and-effect relationships that drive specific stimuli, motives, and behaviors, allows you to manage them by reducing entropy and making more informed decisions. The transformation of employees' thinking through the development of emotional competencies, flexible social skills, and openness enables the creation of more progressive and sustainable teams in the digital economy.

The proposed method for minimizing the risks of communication management in the context of digital transformation involves the development of personalized motivation mechanisms and decision-making pathways. An innovative initiative is viable if there are social forces interested in its implementation. For different groups, this interest is provided in various ways. In this context, the question arises: "How to direct the activities of individuals and groups with specific characteristics and different

structures of motives [22] to participate in innovative events of a specific type?”. When analyzing a given situation, a person evaluates the context based on personal experience and pays special attention to specific nuances. When a consumer sees a car, they conclude whether they like or dislike it. An engineer pays special attention to technical solutions, while a designer focuses on appearance, and so on. The world can only tell a person what she deserves, what she is proportionate to, what she has grown up to, that is, what she can perceive. Primarily, different types of innovative ideas are expected from various kinds of employees [23], ranging from blue-collar workers to operational workers, from white-collar workers to intelligence workers, and from managers and investors to those involved in changing the business model. It is necessary to consider the level of abstraction of an employee engaged in innovation activities, as well as the outlined area of conceivable changes that employees face daily. The focus of perspective is largely determined by the part of the organization involved in executing the employee's functions – whether it is a specific segment of a business process, an entire process, a group of processes, or the organization as a whole. Each of the described groups of employees has its specific innovation potential, degree of autonomy, and characteristic taxonomy of motives that drive innovation efforts. When designing a methodology for evaluating innovative ideas, it is necessary to consider the hidden relative asymmetry of assessments [24], which is expressed in the fact that the perceived usefulness of an idea by a group of people or an individual is not always equivalent to its actual usefulness. The unfairness of the assessment has a detrimental effect on further motivation to innovate. The reverse situation, where an employee's position in the company leads to overestimating the usefulness of their idea, can create an atmosphere of “inequality” among ideas. The risk of excessive subjectivity and evaluation bias is reduced [25] by developing and communicating clearly defined evaluation criteria and principles that can be measured and controlled by employees. However, when the innovator knows the parameters for which optimization is necessary, there is a risk of chasing criteria instead of essential benefits.

The following method of minimizing process risk is an in-depth analysis of the company's internal and external environment to adjust routes and communication mechanisms. Communities of varying degrees of complexity are formed on fundamentally different grounds. For example, for a small firm, the innovative potential [26] of individual employee ideas is more significant than for large organizations, since large firms can create specialized research teams. The specifics should also be taken into account when implementing the methods described earlier. When discussing

corporate culture, the very mechanism of value generation within an organization is crucial – it largely determines the strength of its penetration. For example, the depth of motivation in family firms is usually higher than in corporate ones.

DISCUSSION

There is no [27] only correct way to build a company's communication structure. The preferred models depend on the specific details of the company's external and internal environments. When designing expert knowledge management networks within an enterprise, to increase efficiency, it is necessary to ensure the variability of interaction formats. The communicative framework of the format can determine the space of possible results. When designing a system of collective intelligence, it is essential to consider the potential dangers of intentions, which in some cases can create overly restrictive frames and boundaries.

To mitigate the risk of subjectivity in evaluating innovative ideas, it is essential to develop clear, measurable criteria that are tailored to the specific activities of the company. The most critical catastrophic risks of designing communication systems are: the high proportion of any of the communicating links and the lack of alternative communication routes.

When encouraging staff to innovate, it is necessary to consider the different motivational profiles of various groups and propose mechanisms that are most attractive to them. Conflict is an inevitable consequence of the coexistence of cognitively distinct groups. Cognitive diversity sets the scale of a company's innovation potential. One way to mitigate the destructive effects of emerging conflicts is to develop the emotional intelligence of employees.

Corporate culture is a product of the communication activities that exist within the company. To increase adaptive potential, it is necessary to break down the attitude towards the implementation of ideas put forward by different groups as a zero-sum game. Trust in the solutions developed is a key moment for their effective implementation.

CONCLUSION

The variety of design options for communication structures that lead to economic success indicates the impossibility of using a single, universal solution in this matter. The different economic and value conditions of specific markets may allow for varying

ideologies of company building, such as rigid hierarchies with exclusively top-down, linear connections, and branched heterarchies with 360-degree communications. Proclaiming any variant of building communications in a sociotechnical system as universal for the production of new meanings, techniques, and alternatives is incorrect, as the proposed design can be disastrous in conditions other than those in which it was designed and demonstrated to be effective.

Interacting individuals acquire and actively construct knowledge in dialogue with others, bringing a specific semantic attitude of their personality into this process. The development of a system of interactions increases the capabilities of developing systems by incrementing the sources of their preadaptive potential. The comprehension of new meanings contributes to evolutionary mechanisms that encourage emergent transitions to qualitatively different levels of complexity in the organization. The basis of the coordinate system that defines the methodological optics of decision-making is created by collective reflection, tastes, and styles of thinking. An innovative initiative is viable if there are social forces interested in its implementation. For different groups, this interest is provided in various ways. To fully understand the business environment, effectively allocate limited resources, and launch update processes, it is necessary to populate the management database with diverse worldviews from different employee groups, including both production and administrative staff. Conflict is an inevitable and, if properly controlled, desirable aspect of management and a means of learning.

The prospects for further elaboration of the research topic include expanding the theoretical concepts involved in the analysis, as well as studying specific cases and statistical data on the performance of companies in different cultural and economic contexts to test hypotheses and develop principles for choosing alternative ways to build a communication structure.

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